

Syntheses of some 2-(4'-Acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyl)-coumaran-3-ones

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Syntheses of several 2-(4'-acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones by two routes have been described. In one, the corresponding esters were converted to the related 1,3-diketones which on bromination directly produced 3-bromoflavones. Refluxing of the bromoflavones with ethanolic KOH gave coumaran-3-ones. In the second route the corresponding esters were brominated using CuBr, to yield α -bromoacetophenones which on Baker-Venkataraman transformation directly afforded the desired product. The structure of the aurones were confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data.

A few coumaran-3-ones containing a nitro group in benzoyl part of the substituent at the position-2 were prepared for the first time in our laboratory¹. Since the number of such compounds prepared are few, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise more such compounds. It was planned that the benzoyl group would carry an acetamido group at position-4' and also a nitro group at position-3' (Scheme 1).

4'-Acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyloxyacetophenone (2) were prepared by directly condensing the 2-hydroxyacetophenones with known 4-acetamido-3-nitrobenzoic acid. The esters (2) on Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement gave the corresponding 2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane derivatives (3a-1). These β -diketones were brominated with bromine in dioxan at room temperature to obtain the 3-bromoflavones (5a-1) via the monobromodibenzoyl compounds (4a-1) as postulated by earlier workers². On boiling the 3-bromoflavones with ethanolic KOH the corresponding coumaran-3-ones (6a-1) were produced in good yields. Compounds (6a-1) were found soluble in alkali and gave positive ferric reaction. These analysed correctly for C and H. The ir spectra agreed with the structure and a distinct hydroxyl band was noticable and pmr spectra of four representative compounds confirmed the structure.

Scheme 2 was designed to obtain the same coumaran-3-ones.

The esters (2) on bromination with cupric bromide in dry dioxan afforded the ω -bromoacetophenones (7), which on refluxing with powdered KOH in dioxan produced the coumaran-3-ones, obviously through the unstable product 4. The yields were excellent. The compounds obtained by this route were identical with the coumaran-3-ones obtained by Scheme 1. The overall yields by Scheme 2 were better than Scheme 1.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded

on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer and pmr spectra (90 MHz) in deuteriochloroform.

4-Acetamido-3-nitrobenzoyloxyacetophenones (2a-1): The compounds were prepared from *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (1; 0.0065 mol) and 4-acetamido-3-nitrobenzoic acid (0.007 mol) in the usual manner³⁻⁷ in 50-85% yields: **2a** m.p. 83-84° (EtOH); **b** 145° (EtOAc); **c** 150-51° (EtOH); **d** 168-69° (EtOH); **e** 175-76° (EtOH), **f** 78-79° (EtOAc); **g** 127-28° (MeOH); **h** 80-81° (EtOH); **i** 205-06° (EtOH); **j** 200-01° (MeOH); **k** 75° (EtOH); **l** 105-06° (MeOH).

2-Hydroxy- ω -(4-acetamido-3-nitrobenzoyl)acetophenones (3a-1): A mixture of benzoyloxyacetophenones (2; 0.001 mol) in dry pyridine (30-35 ml) and powdered KOH was stirred at about 80° for 2-3 h avoiding moisture. The viscous dark red mass obtained was decomposed with ice-cold HCl and worked up to yield (50-85%) the products: **3a** m.p. 143-44° (EtOAc); **b** 210-11° (EtOAc); **c** 210° (EtOH); **d** 198-200° (EtOAc); **e** 239-40° (EtOAc); **f** 154-55° (EtOAc); **g** 183-84° (EtOH); **h** 140-41° (EtOH); **i** 260-61° (EtOAc); **j** 200-01° (MeOH); **k** 180-81° (CHCl₃); **l** 175-76° (EtOH).

3-Bromo-2-(4'-acetamido-3'-nitrophenyl)flavone (5a-1): To a solution of **3a-1** (0.001 mol) in anhydrous dioxan (30 ml), bromine (0.0025 mol) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture on then poured into a large volume of ice-cold water and the resulting crude products were worked up to yield (60-80%) the compounds: **5a** m.p. 263° (AcOH); **b** 225° (EtOAc); **c** 195° (EtOH); **d** 184° (EtOH); **e** 245° (EtOH); **f** 192° (EtOH+EtOAc); **g** 242-43° (EtOAc); **h** 205-06° (AcOH); **i** 321-22° (AcOH); **j** 310-11° (EtOAc); **k** 245-46° (AcOH); **l** 235-36° (EtOAc).

2-(4'-Acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (6a-1): To **5a-1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), ethanolic KOH (10 ml, 25%) was added and the mixture was gently refluxed for 2 h. The mixture was then cooled and treated with ice-cold HCl and

- a : R₁=CH₃, R₂=H, R₃=Br b : R₁=R₂=Br, R₃=CH₃
 c : R₁=R₂=H, R₃=CH₃ d : R₁=R₂=H, R₃=Cl
 e : R₁=Br, R₂=H, R₃=Cl f : R₁=R₂=Br, R₃=H
 g : R₁=R₂=R₃=H h : R₁=R₂=R₃=Br
 i : R₁=CH₃, R₂=R₃=H j : R₁=R₂=H, R₃=CH₃
 k : R₁=Br, R₂=H, R₃=CH₃ l : R₁=H, R₂=CH₃, R₃=Br

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

the resulting solid was recrystallised $\therefore$ 6a, m.p. 195° (EtOH), δ (DMSO-d₆; 90 MHz) 2.10 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 2.17 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.4–3.25 (DMSO-d₆ band), hydroxy proton merges with aromatic protons and appears as multiplet 7.5–8.7 (6H, m, ArH); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 085 (chelated OH), 1 635 (C=O) and 745 cm⁻¹ (NHCOCH₃); b 184° (EtOAc+pet. ether); c 190° (EtOH); d 178° (EtOH); δ (DMSO-d₆; 90 MHz) 2.10 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 2.4–3.25, hydroxyl proton merges with aromatic protons and appears as multiplet (7H, m, ArH); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 110 (chelated OH), 1 625 (C=O) and 750 cm⁻¹ (NHCOCH₃); e 245° (EtOH); f 192° (EtOH+EtOAc); g 210° (AcOH); h 185° (EtOH+pet. ether), δ (DMSO-d₆; 90 MHz) 2.30 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 2.42, hydroxyl proton merges with aromatic proton and appears as multiplet at 7.2–9.1 (7H, m, ArH); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 120 (chelated OH), 1 620 (C=O) and 740 cm⁻¹ (NHCOCH₃); i 215–16° (AcOH); j 315–16° (AcOH); k 205–06° (AcOH); l 145–46° (EtOH+CHCl₃); δ (DMSO-d₆; 90 MHz) 2.10 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 2.20 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.42, hydroxyl proton merges with aromatic protons and appears as multiplet at 7.5–8.7 (6H, m); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 115 (chelated OH), 1 630 (C=O) and 755 cm⁻¹ (NHCOCH₃).

2-(4'-Acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyl)- ω -bromoacetophenones (7a-1): A suspension of finely powdered dry cupric bromide (0.02 mol) in anhydrous dioxan (60 ml) was refluxed for 30 min in anhydrous condition and 2 (0.01 mol) was then added to it and refluxing was continued till a grey white precipitate of cuprous bromide was obtained (13–14 h) and work up to yield the products (5.5–80%): 7a m.p. 135–36° (EtOH); b 110–11° (EtOAc); c 121–22° (aqueous AcOH); d 103–04° (EtOH); e 145° (MeOH); f 66° (EtOAc); g 75–86° (EtOH); h 65–66° (MeOH); i 184–85° (EtOH); j 146–47° (EtOH); k gymmy mass; l 75–76° (EtOH).

Method II. 2-(4'-Acetamido-3'-nitrobenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (6a-1): To the ω -bromoester (7; 0.01 mol) in dioxan (30 ml) powdered KOH (0.03 mol) was added and the mixture was gently refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and treatment with ice-cold HCl solution gave crude product which was recrystallised.

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